

Orhan Kılıç

Department of History, Faculty of Human and Social Sciences, Firat University
23119 Elâzığ Merkez, Elazığ, Turkey
E-mail: okilic60@gmail.com

PREVENTIVE MEASURES AND TREATMENT METHODS OF EPIDEMICS AND INFECTIOUS DISEASES IN THE OTTOMAN SOCIETY

Abstract: Until the causes of infectious and epidemic diseases are known for certain and modern treatment methods are found, some measures have been taken to prevent diseases in all societies. In case of emergence of diseases, some traditional treatment methods have been applied. Living in clean and hygienic environments can be considered the most realistic measure to prevent the emergence of infectious diseases. However, it is seen that the concept of cleaning is perceived differently at different times, especially in Europe. Since Muslims lived predominantly in the Ottoman Empire, it can be said that they acted sensitively about body cleaning as a command of their religion. In addition to cleaning and hygiene, strengthening the immune system with natural remedies can be expressed as one of the most prominent measures. One of the most realistic measures was not to leave the diseased place and not to enter the diseased place. The quarantine application should also be evaluated in this context. There is information that the first vaccinations against smallpox were made by traditional methods in the Ottoman society. Herbal medicines were the most common form of treatment when infectious diseases emerged as an epidemic and deeply affected the society. Cassidoni (*Lavandula stoechas*), Nevruziye paste, henna, goat's milk surutka, mışmış, isfanah, razıyanec, şibrem and honey are just a few of the natural remedies. Apart from these, it is also known that drugs are made with surgical methods and some chemical compositions. There were also some magical practices such as witchcraft, voodoo, talisman and fortune-telling in order not to get sick or to be treated. In this context, it is possible to evaluate the lodges of the poor and pesthouse, where leprosy patients are treated and isolated.

Key words: epidemics, infectious disease

Non MeSH: Ottoman, natural medicine, isolation

Introduction

Traditional measures and treatment methods have been used in the fight against epidemics and infectious diseases until the microorganisms that cause diseases became known, and realistic and scientific measures and treatment methods are found with medical methods. In addition, it is necessary to express some psychological measures based on the traditional belief system in this context.

The fact that the gods of sickness were seen in the belief system of the Hittites and other societies in ancient times shows that they were accepted as the most important protective measure. Such behavior has caused helpless people to enter into a psychological comfort and at least experience the peace as if they had taken necessary precautions.

The main function of herbal fragrances in ancient Greece was to heal. The famous lyric poet of antiquity, Anacreon, suggested rubbing the chest with ointments to prevent diseases. [1 p28] These scientific and non-medical measures were not, of course, to prevent the spread of epidemics. However, medical science was not developed enough to prevent contagious diseases from turning into epidemics. Due to the inadequacy of medical science, the struggle against the plague in the New Age consisted of cordoning off the contaminated areas, lighting fires in the streets where the disease was seen, soaking the walls of the houses with absinthe or vinegar, and a quarantine facility. [2 p319]

Throughout the history, the most important precaution that people took against infectious diseases was to leave the place where the contagious disease was seen. This was the most common measure in Europe. This state of panic could not prevent the contagious disease from spreading to wider geographies.

Psychological measures rooted in the traditional belief system were also quite common. The most typical example of this is that the Hittites wished that they would not be infected by the plague through the plague gods and made some prayers. [3] The establishment of cemeteries outside the cities is also a result of the concern that the disease will spread from the graves. Romans made offerings of food and drink to their dead on certain days of the year. Food and drink were poured into the pipes leading down to the tomb. [4 p23] *Winnebagos* near the Great Lakes in America tried to scare away smallpox with dead dogs they hung on trees. [5 p107] All these practices should be regarded as psychological measures.

The quarantine practice, known to have existed since antiquity, but institutionalized in the last quarter of the 15th century, should also be regarded as one of the measures taken. In the world outside the Ottoman Empire, it is possible to express environmental regulations and improvement in the historical process and vaccination applications in recent times as other measures taken.

Treatment methods, on the other hand, were carried out using traditional ways, such as precautions, the cause of the emergence of diseases, knowing the microbes that cause diseases, finding the drugs that can be used against them, and vaccination practices. Methods such as herbal medicines, surgical and chemical methods, psychological and traditional methods were also implemented.

Measures to Prevent Infectious and Epidemic Diseases in Ottoman Society

Having hygienic and clean environment that do not allow the reproduction of microbes can be expressed as the most realistic measure to prevent the emergence and spread of epidemic diseases. Of course, this does not apply to all kinds of diseases. However, cleanliness, healthy environmental conditions and nutrition in a way that strengthens immunity can be mentioned as measures that have not changed in every period of history in the fight against diseases. In this respect, people should meticulously comply with both their personal hygiene and environmental cleanliness (sanitation).

Personal and Environmental Cleaning

When the causes of epidemics became clear, there were changes in the understanding of cleanliness and hygiene of people and societies. When evaluated in the context of the religions they belonged to, Christians were more negatively affected by epidemics than Jews and Muslims, because body cleaning and hygiene were not seen as a requirement of their religion. According to Christian belief, the person who was bathed at Baptism did not need any further cleansing. However, this spiritual cleansing did not provide any protection against fleas that carry the plague. This situation has revealed that Christian societies need to make a radical change in their bathroom and toilet cultures. [6 p130]

Bathing and bath culture was a religious obligation in Muslim societies. The fact that sexual intercourse outside of marriage is not permissible by religion has led to a lower incidence of venereal diseases such as syphilis. However, in order for the microorganisms that cause diseases not to be transmitted to people, it was not enough to just follow the rules of personal hygiene or fulfill religious obligations, the society had to be conscious and ready for it. It is difficult to say that the Islamic world is meticulous about environmental cleanliness and personal hygiene. Therefore, it is more important whether people are open to transportation and the spread of microbes rather than which religion they belong to.

There are also observations that contradict the views that environmental cleanliness was not given enough importance in Ottoman society. *Ulrich Jasper Seetzen*, a German medical doctor who visited Istanbul in 1803 and who is also interested in natural history, did not agree with the views of many people that the outbreak and spread of plague epidemics was caused by the Turks not paying enough attention to hygiene. He says that there are practices that can be shown as examples for bodily cleaning applied by the Turks to the peoples of Europe especially such as the ghusl and ablution as matters of religious obligation and the prevalence of the bath culture. [7 p80-81]

Since personal hygiene was a religious obligation in Ottoman society, precautions were taken to produce mostly basic food products under hygienic conditions and to deliver them to the consumer without spoiling. Italian Luigi Bassano, who stayed in the Ottoman Empire and especially in Istanbul between 1532 and 1540, says that no one should be surprised that there is not as much infection among the Turks as in his own country. According to Bassano, the Turks acted cautiously against contagious di-

seases due to living a simple life and other reasons. It records that no animals are slaughtered, leather is tanned, or they do not do any work or process that will cause bad odor in the cities. [8 p93]. During the reign of Mehmed I, two sweepers were appointed for each street of Istanbul, and they cleaned the saliva with lime dust and coal ash. In Edirne in 1539 it has been warned that no one should throw garbage in front of the house shop, that the dirty water of the baths should not be discharged to the streets, that toilets should not be built on the canals made for this purpose, that animal droppings and carcasses should not be left in the middle and should be collected, and that bleach should not be spilled on the roads. It is also been determined that, with an order dated to 1695, the collected shrines be dumped into the sea with a wrong decision. The most rooted regulation on environmental cleaning in the Ottoman Empire was published in 1719. According to this regulation, it was decided to appoint two or three sweepers to each neighborhood in order to eliminate animal carcasses, slaughterhouses and filth in the bazaars and streets, to collect their wages from the houses and shops, and to be controlled by the neighborhood imams. [9 p319-20] There are also observations of some bad practices. Michael Heberer, who was a slave in Ottoman galleys between 1585 and 1588, wrote in his memoirs that the streets of Istanbul were very dirty and smelled badly, that he came across the carcasses of horses, dogs and cats a lot in the middle of the street, and that it should not be surprising that deadly epidemics broke out in these conditions. [10 p253] Palace composer Santurî Ali Ufki Bey, in his memoirs about the middle of the 17th century, associated the plague epidemic that broke out in Edirne Palace to the Feast of Sacrifice, which coincides with spring. He states that the sun hitting the blood and offal of the animals slaughtered during the feast causes a very bad smell, and it is believed that this is why the plague started. [11 p49]

Famous French traveler Jean Baptiste Tavernier, who visited Izmir in 1632, says that there was a plague epidemic in the city almost every year, and the reason for this was that the abundant stinking water that accumulated around the city during the winter was not discharged properly. [12 p117]

Epidemics usually spread through trade routes. For this reason, coastal and port cities were among the most affected places. The intersections of important roads on land routes also suffered the same fate. The disease was naturally less common in the interior. Another reason was pilgrimage. During the pilgrimage, the diseases spread and many people died. Epidemics originating from the pilgrimage also hit the interior. [13 p346]

Escape or Isolation as a Precaution

The most common measure used in almost every society as protection from epidemics and contagious diseases was to leave the epidemic location in a hurry. Leaving the diseased place also engendered a negative result, such as the spread of the microbe to the areas visited. The desire of the people to leave the location where plague or epidemic emerged also created a two-way negativity. The first of these is the disruption of the service to be fulfilled in the abandoned area, and the second is that the evacuated places are subject to banditry activities. In the middle of the 16th century, tem-

porary migrations after the plague epidemic in Thessaloniki [14 p201] and Alacahisar [15 p71] caused disruption of services. Due to the plague epidemic in the city of Edirne and Hasköy in the 16th century, some of the villagers left the region, leaving the area empty and such places mostly became a place where bandits came and looted. [16 p38]

Christians who were on duty as an embassy in the Ottoman Empire were not allowed to leave the city and their places during the plague epidemic in Istanbul. Because of this sanction, the foreign missions in Pera stayed in their houses in the vineyards of Pera when there was an epidemic in the city. In 1612, when the epidemic spread to the palace and one of his sisters died from the plague, Sultan Ahmed I, passed to one of the cottage houses called Davut Pasha Palace following the advice of Nâsuh Pasha. [17 p372-73]

The Islamic world adopted a more plausible practice, which could perhaps be thought of as a more fatalistic approach in this regard. Muslims believe that even if they die, they will be martyrs if they do not leave the place where the plague is infected or if they do not enter a place where there is a plague epidemic. Because there are hadiths about it. [18 p527] The basic expectation in these hadiths was that people would be warned about it with an otherworldly reward, out of fear that the disease would spread.

During the plague epidemic in 1812, some wealthy people moved to the Anatolian side, where malaria, which is less dangerous than the plague, prevailed. Mehmed III did not return to Topkapı Palace until 1598, when the plague wave that besieged Topkapı and the Old Palace abated. In the fatwa issued by Ebussuud Efendi, the sheikh al-Islam of the time, in the 16th century, on whether it is permissible to escape from the plague, the provision that *it is permissible to escape the wrath of Allah and to seek his help supports the idea of escaping the plague* when people find the opportunity. [19 p84]

Mustafa Behçet, the chief physician of the period, who wrote a pamphlet during the cholera epidemic that broke out in Istanbul in 1831, noted that the main way of preventing the disease was to stay away from the sick. [20 p64] It is also possible to evaluate this precaution as not to enter the diseased place or to stay away.

Traditional Faith-Based Psychological Measures

One of the important elements used in the fight against epidemics, prevention and treatment is the psychological methods that originate from various local beliefs and are largely supported by the belief system. Talismans, prayers, curses or traditional folk beliefs also contain some motifs for the prevention of epidemics.

Among the causes of the plague are the presence of microbes in the air and the adverse conditions in the air. In order to prevent these, it is important that the fluids in the human body are balanced. Among the psychological measures taken to prevent these in Ottoman society, such things can be listed as keeping a quiet attitude, leading an orderly life and staying away from pushing oneself too much, getting angry and getting excited. [21 p155-56]

Strengthening the Immune System and Environmental Disinfection with Natural Medicines

The foremost of the measures taken to prevent diseases is to strengthen the immune system with natural herbs or medicines. It was believed that raw onion, lentil, lemon, pomegranate or grape juice [21 p156], garlic, novruziyye or mesir paste with vinegar, consumed in moderation, strengthens the immune system and reduces the risk of contracting epidemics. These medicines were also used for the treatment of infectious diseases.

Since contagious diseases are thought to be caused by microbes (miyazma), it is seen that fragrant incense, which helps to destroy this bad air, is widely used in the eastern and western world. Euchard and sulfur are other common ingredients used to make incense. Bran mixed with saltpeter and olive oil was scattered on the fire, which was burned in order to obtain the smoke needed to disinfect all kinds of commercial goods or documents coming to the quarantine. The inhabited parts of the houses were smoked with salt spirit smoke, and the empty parts with salt spirit and Güher bitter smoke. [2 p321] Evliya Çelebi, who visited the city of Engiri (Ergiri) in 1670, writes that the people living here did not enter the house where bubonic plague was seen for a few years. He states that if they need to enter, they wash that house with vinegar, smoke it with various scents, wash and repair many parts of it, and use it after whitewashing their rooms with white lime. [22 p349-50] German traveler Ulrich Jasper Seetzen tells that in 1803, two letters he sent from Istanbul to Vienna and Leipzig were thrown into a chest on a grate, which stood outside without a stamp on it. [7 p116-17]

As with other diseases, some precautions were taken to avoid cholera disease. In the Cholera Booklet prepared by Chief Physician Mustafa Behçet, it was stated that the cause of cholera was *bile*, and it was requested to avoid foods that increase bile. Small amounts of light meals should be preferred instead of heavy fatty meals. It was stated that all dishes cooked with olive oil paved the way for cholera, because olive oil has the property of burning bile. In addition, pastries, milk and dairy products and eggs should be avoided since they turned into bile immediately. Fruits such as plums, peaches, melons, watermelons, apricots and cucumbers should not be consumed as they quickly turn into bile. Apple, pomegranate, verjuice, sour sherbets, lemonade vinegar (a mixture of vinegar and honey) could be used, but not excessively. It should be drunk by adding a small amount of vinegar to the drinking water. It was appropriate that Chief Physician Mustafa Behçet Efendi recommended sour foods and drinks. Because after the cause of the disease was found, it was understood that cholera vibrios could not hold on in the acid environment. It has been observed that those who eat onions and garlic did not contract this disease. Apart from this, in the treatise in question, recommendations were made about the foods to be consumed before and during cholera infection. [20 p64]

Quarantine Measures

The most important and perhaps the most realistic of the measures taken to prevent the spread of epidemics and infectious diseases is the quarantine application. Qu-

arantine measures were applied in the first periods when epidemics caused mass deaths, especially in port cities, even if not with modern methods, not to let ships known to be sick into the port by throwing fireballs. The quarantine system did not undertake a function related to the treatment of the disease. Because treatment with the active drug was yet to be realized. The practice consisted of keeping them waiting for a reasonable period of time, depending on the type of disease, for those who would go to another country or city by land or sea, until modern quarantine systems were established. According to the information given by Evliya Çelebi, Istanbul Yedikule was a place where those coming from the plague-ridden settlements were left for seven days before they were allowed to enter. [23 p129]

It can be said that a quarantine practice was established in the Ottoman Empire, even if not with modern methods, in the 16th century. An example of this is the practice in Chios. In 1566, it was said that the merchants who came to Chios from outside were *told that they came from the place of the plague*, and they were imprisoned for 25 days and their 2 coins were taken a day. [24 p492] It is stated that in the 16th and 17th centuries, the plague spread in the port cities of the Ottoman Empire and in the cities and towns on the trade routes from the merchant ships coming from the Mediterranean ports and the caravans coming from Asia, and it caused great losses because no precautions were taken. An anonymous travelogue dated 1621 records that the plague was generally spread by ships from Egypt. [17 p372]

During the times when the plague epidemic was widespread, no one was allowed to enter the cities comfortably, and beggars and vagrants were not allowed into the cities. [2 p319] Especially in cities surrounded by walls, the gates were opened with the sunrise and closed with the sunset. It is seen that this measure taken for control purposes was applied in some cities until a hundred and fifty years ago. For example, the traveler H. Petermann, who visited Diyarbakir in 1853, had to wait for the morning when he arrived shortly after the sun went down, as the city gates were closed. [25 p20]

It is stated that the first institutional quarantine practices in the Ottoman Empire started with the establishment of the quarantine system in Egypt in 1813 by Mehmet Ali Pasha due to the news of the plague from Istanbul and the outbreak of the plague epidemic in port cities, especially in Alexandria. In port cities such as Alexandria and Damietta, quarantine measures were introduced during epidemics in 1814, 1819 and 1821. A quarantine was established in Beirut in 1834 by means of İbrahim Pasha, who ruled Syria on behalf of Mehmet Ali Pasha. [26 p712-13] Since these practices took place in a region not directly under Ottoman rule, it is accepted that the first quarantine practices in the Ottoman Empire started during the 1831 cholera epidemic. [27 p463]

Vaccination

Information about the vaccine made from smallpox reached Europe not from African slaves, but from the Ottoman Empire in a different way. Lady Mary Wortley Montagu, the wife of the British ambassador in Istanbul, stated in a letter she wrote from Istanbul in 1717 that she did not catch smallpox by a method that locals call in-lay. She wrote that there is a group of old women who do this as a job every September,

and that the old woman stuffs the strongest smallpox substance into a hazelnut shell and puts the substance in the shell into the vein as much as the tip of her needle can take. Lady Montagu's stories about Turkish village women opened a way in England to the principle of vaccination, and in the next period, a family of humble doctors, Robert Sutton and his sons, developed an easy, reliable and cheap method and enabled the vaccination of the masses thus realizing a groundbreaking innovation. [28 p110-15]

Treatment Methods

Epidemic and contagious diseases were not seen as a microbiological phenomenon in the Ancient, Middle and New Ages. Some medieval physicians, such as Ibn Sina, thought that some invisible microbes caused diseases, but they could not put forward their theories clearly because they did not have a microscope or similar technical equipment. Because of this limitation, the prevailing view in almost all societies was that contagious diseases were a scourge sent by God to punish people. Psychological and traditional treatment methods were used until the way of treating diseases with medical methods was established.

Treatment with Natural Medicines

Herbal medicines were either prepared by combining several plants with various methods, or a single plant could be used for therapeutic or preventive purposes in various ways.

At the beginning of the 19th century, there are observations that the nurses in a hospital belonging to the Jews of Izmir, and where the plague patients were hospitalized, constantly ate copious amounts of onions and garlic and drank bottles of spirits. It was noted that, among these nurses, was rare to find people who contract the plague and died. [29 p502]

Known as *blackhead grass* (*Lavandula stoechas*), but also called *false lavender*, *gargan* and *monk grass*, it is known that the plant was used as a cure for cholera as well as many other diseases. The reason why this herb is called monk herb is because it is found in Uludağ, formerly known as the *Monk Mountain*. It was a concoction that was used frequently, especially by the Ottomans. It was even used in the treatment during the cholera epidemics during the Ottoman period and it was sold in pharmacies. In addition to its relaxing and soothing effect, it can be said that it is effective against microorganisms such as viruses, bacteria and fungi, and it is still being used. [30 p39, 31 p26] It is mentioned in the sources that forty kinds of spices are made by combining a red colored paste called Nevruziye and mesir paste made from 61 kinds of spices are good for pestilence and plague fevers. [32 p4, p96]

Evliya Çelebi wrote that there was a lot of malaria in the town of Gebela in Herzegovina. He records that the townspeople were fit and strong enough to endure the heat and row with intoxicating drinks such as *goat's milk surutka* or *pivo* and *honey juice*. [33 p284] He also records that in Adalya (Antalya) people ate lemons to get rid of fever and that lemon tore down the bile and phlegm and cured all diseases. [34 p148]

Naïma Mustafa Efendi says that the fig grown on the island of Lemnos is famous, and a priest there developed a medicine from this fig and sent it to the kings and emperors of the period as a cure for many diseases, and sold it to the merchants as well. Mustafa Efendi even records that he became famous in Lemnos with the name of *tin-i râhib*, priest of figs. Mustafa Efendi also stated that this fig and medicine made from it were very beneficial for *hummâ-yı vebâ'iyye* (fever from plague) and pestilence, as well as for many other diseases. [35 p1692]

Some of the foods that Ottoman cosmographer Âşık Mehmed recorded in his work as preventive and therapeutic for malaria are as follows:

Mışmış [apricot]: The fresh fruit causes fever. Dried one cures fever. [36 p1259]

İsfânâh [spinach]: This spice is said to cure fever. It is stated that it is not advised to eat more than one dirham (3,207 gr.). [36 p1273]

Râziyâneç [fennel]: Destroys various types of fever diseases. [36 p1279]

Şibrem [Euphorbia chamaesyce]: It causes fever; when taken in two dirhams, it's a deadly poison. [36, p1299]

Dik [rooster]: It is said that its meat is good for fever. [36 pp1562]

Honey: It is protective and therapeutic against malaria. [36 pp1663-65]

Katip Çelebi, while giving information about the city of *Ubullâ* in the Basra region, says that there is a shrine where the graves of the Companions are located, and that the steam of the bark of the giant cherry trees in this holy place is used to relieve fever. [37 p541-42]

The most effective thing in the bouts of fever experienced by malaria patients was to wash with cold water or make ice compresses. Katip Çelebi writes that the water of the lake in the Kuba village of Tarhu, one of the important cities of Georgia, is warm in spring and autumn, hot in winter and very cold in summer, and that the people of this district use the ice they extract from it for fever and other febrile diseases. [37 p491-92]

Âşık Mehmed gives many examples about the treatment methods of leprosy. Some of these are those:

Hacer-i ziftî: It is a black stone. Similar to pitch. If the beaten powder is mixed with rose oil and applied to leprosy, yellow waters flow and the patient recovers health. [36 p1216]

Hacer-i Târidü'n-nevm: It is a white stone. There are other colors as well. Whoever hangs a little piece of this stone cannot sleep. Half a dirham amount destroys leprosy. [36 p1218]

Hacer-i Kirmânî: It is a black stone. If the dust of this stone is mixed with salt and applied to leprosy, it will heal. [36 p1222]

Büdâyiş: It's a theriac (antidote consisting of animal and herbal mixtures). It destroys berâs and leprosy. [36 p1291]

Fûtenc: It is understood to be a plant species. If a small amount is eaten, it is good for leprosy. [36 p1312-13]

Düldül: It is an animal called shanger in Persian and hedgehog in Turkish. Its meat is good for leprosy and berâs. [36 p1330]

Treatment with Surgical and Chemical Methods

In addition to natural medicines and surgical methods in the treatment of diseases, some views and techniques have developed regarding the treatment with drugs produced by applying chemical methods. In a memoir penned by a Spaniard, who lived as a slave in the Ottoman Empire between the years of 1552-1556, and which was presented to the King of Spain, Philip II in 1557, it was mentioned that the prisoner in question survived tuberculosis by having his blood drawn. [38 p31]

A physician who was among the German-Austrian embassy delegation that came to Istanbul in 1592, treated the people in following way: they were removed from a tower, where they were closed every day due to the request of the citizens, because of the plague epidemic outbreak while the embassy was kept in prison. This physician applied a treatment consisting of puncturing a vein in the arm of about twenty to thirty patients a day; they were brought to him and their blood was drained. He became a respected person because he did not hurt the patients during the procedure. When doctors usually did this operation with Italian knives, they caused great wounds on patient's arms, so they suffered a lot. [39 p134-35] The expectation of the bloodletting practice was to drain the infected blood in the body and replace it with clean blood and to maintain the fluid balance in the body. Leeches were also used for this treatment. [40 p74]

Psychological and Traditional Treatment Methods

The most common method used in the treatment of infectious diseases was psychological and conventional therapy. It was a widespread understanding that diseases were God's punishment. Because, understandably, in eras when the role of microbes in diseases' origins and spreading was not known, people attributed a divine aspect to diseases and relieved themselves psychologically in this way. Since ancient times, sanctifying diseases and including some disease gods in the belief system are examples that support this view.

German galley slave named Heberer mentions that a kind of soil called *terra sigillata* on the island of Lemnos had very valuable properties and that this soil was used as a medicine against plague and poisoning. He says that it was only possible to get the *terra sigillata* by digging from the ground on August 6, that day the Turks dug the soil with ceremonies and wrote something on it in Arabic letters, calling that soil the "sealed soil". [10 p259] This narrative suggests that the soil in question was used not as a material medicine, but as a psychological or magical treatment tool.

The most striking thing about leprosy is that while the disease was almost disappearing from the 15th century in Europe, it would continue to affect the Eastern world for a longer period of time. It is also seen that some religious motifs were used in the treatment of leprosy and an attempt was made to reduce the suffering of the patients by keeping their spirituality high. Magic treatment methods were used for leprosy as well as for other diseases. Physicians of the period were trying to treat patients with some herbal or animal extracts. It is possible to say that traditional treatment methods were at the forefront, until the establishment of leprosy hospitals.

Evliya Çelebi, while giving information about the Prophet Shuayb, whose tomb he visited during his pilgrimage, also talks about a folk belief regarding the treatment of the lepers. According to this folk belief, it was said that the people with leprosy were healed if they drank the water that was previously put in a hollow, which was considered to be the left footprint of Prophet Moses. [34 p223]

Evliya Çelebi records another religious or magical treatment method, which he did not personally witness, but which was witnessed by many people from the province instead, was held in Pravadi. According to this belief, the patient with leprosy was cured as a result of the scraping and licking of the third of the tombstones found during the *Visit to the Seven* in Pravadi. [41 p177]

Since leprosy is apparently a skin disease, it is common for patients to seek healing in various water sources or hot springs. The most important source reflecting the situation in the 17th century is the Travel Book of Evliya Çelebi. Evliya Çelebi writes that those who take ghusl in the water of the water source called *Ayn-ı Balıklı (Fish Spring)* in the city of Diyarbakir get rid of fever and leprosy. [42 p28] He notes that the Çekirge thermal spring in Bursa [43 p18] and the thermal springs in the city of Donkola, which he saw during his trip to Africa, cured stagnancy as well as many other diseases. [44 p455] Apart from these, he says that there was *Hallez Hot Spring* by a small river flowing under the village called Hallez, one and a half hours away from Ladik. He records that the hot spring was domed, and that during the cherry season, thousands of people from all over the region got rid of leprosy by swimming in this hot spring. [45 p176]

Disinfect and Treatment

We have pointed out that the most important and indispensable procedure that should be used in the prevention and treatment of epidemics is disinfection. Disinfection studies were a must-do in order to prevent the emergence of a disease and to mitigate or completely eliminate the effect of the disease after it appeared. Cleaning the microbes from the living environment means preventing the active effect of the disease. In historical periods, each community has focused on disinfecting their environment according to their own understanding of cleanliness and hygiene, or the understanding of cleanliness in the treatment of wounds resulting from diseases.

It is seen that disinfection was not widely used in the treatment of infectious diseases, especially in the Christian world, until the end of the Early modern era. In those times, the plague was still a mystery to the Western world. H. Von Moltke, who gave information about the plague epidemics in Istanbul in 1837, said: *The plague is an unsolved mystery. This is the mystery of Sphinx that cost the life of the person who tried to solve it even before he succeeded. This is what happened to French doctors in Egypt.* [46 p87-8] This situation came to the fore during Napoleon's siege of Akka Castle in 1798. During this siege, plague broke out in Napoleon's army and when they became helpless against the disease, soldiers were advised to drink opium and were left to die instead of being carried from city to city. [47 p56]

Another issue that can be considered as a precaution rather than a cure is the advantage of nomadic lifestyle regarding contracting epidemics. Moving and living in sparsely populated areas reduced the risk of direct contact with other humans, so nomads faced fewer epidemics. They continued on their way by burying the deceased tribe members either in the cemetery of a nearby village or in the place where they died. Another interesting factor was that the smell of horses and goats killed fleas that carried epidemics or plague. Nomads, who were mainly horse and goat breeders, were thus more protected against epidemic diseases. [48 p122]

Conclusion

Infectious and epidemic diseases are one of the most important factors affecting human history in many respects. Throughout history, people have had to struggle with microbes they did not know about. Epidemics have had serious effects on political and military history, economic, social and cultural life.

It is possible to say that measures and treatments had been carried out with traditional methods until the cause, prevention and treatment of infectious diseases were found. Measures and treatments varied according to geography and religion. For a long time, in all religions and geographies, epidemics and contagious diseases were sanctified.

References:

1. Hurton A. Parfümün Erotizmi Güzel Kokuların Tarihi [The Eroticism of Perfume. The History of Fine Fragrances]. İstanbul: Kabalıcı Press; 1995.
2. Kolling O. XVIII. Asırda Veba Salgını Devirlerinde Ticaret Münasebetleri [Trade Relations in the Age of Plague Epidemic in the 18th Century]. Ülkü. 1941 Haziran;21(100):317-24.
3. Arıkan Y. II. Mursili'nin Veba Duaları [Mursili's II Plague Prayers]. Ankara Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Eskiçağ Dilleri ve Kültürleri Bölümü, (Hititoloji Anabilim Dalı); 1994.
4. Howitt C. Antik Dünya'da Bilinmesi Gereken 500 Şey [500 Things to Know in the Ancient World]. İstanbul: Türkiye İş Bankası Kültür Press; 2009.
5. Nikiforuk A. Mahşerin Dördüncü Atlısı Salgın ve Bulaşıcı Hastalıklar Tarihi [The Fourth Horseman of the Apocalypse. The History of Epidemics and Infectious Diseases]. Second Edition. İstanbul: İletişim Press; 2001.
6. Tannahill R. Tarihte Cinsellik [Sexuality in History]. Ankara: Dost Kitabevi; Ekim 2003.
7. Seetzen UJ. İstanbul Günlükleri ve Anadolu'da Yolculuk 12 Aralık 1802-22 Haziran 1803 [İstanbul Diaries and Journey in Anatolia 12 December 1802-22 June 1803]. Vol. 1. First Edition. İstanbul 2017.
8. Bassano L. Kanunî Dönemi Osmanlı İmparatorluğu'nda Gündelik Hayat [Everyday Life in the Ottoman Empire in the Kanuni Period]. İstanbul: Yeditepe Press; Nisan 2011.

9. Sarıyıldız G. Hıfzıssıhha-Osmanlılar'da Hıfzıssıhha [Hygiene of the Ottomans], *DİA*, C. 17, İstanbul: Türkiye Diyanet Vakfı Press; 1998, pp. 319-320.
10. Heberer M. Osmanlıda Bir Köle Brettenli Michael Heberer'in Anıları 1585-1588 [A Slave in the Ottoman Empire. Memoirs of Michael Heberer von Bretten 1585-1588]. İstanbul: Kitap Yayınevi Press; Haziran 2003.
11. Bobovius A. Albertus Bobovius ya da Santuri Ali Ufki Bey'in Anıları Topkapı Sarayı'nda Yaşam [Memoirs of Albertus Bobovius or Santuri Ali Ufki Bey. Life in Topkapı Palace]. Yerasimos S, Berthier A, editors. İstanbul: Kitap Press; 2002.
12. Tavernier JB. Tavernier Seyahatnamesi [Tavernier Travelogue]. Yerasimos S, editor. Second Edition. İstanbul: Kitap Yayınevi Press; Şubat 2010.
13. McCarty J. Osmanlı Türkleri 1281'den 1923'e [Ottoman Turks from 1281 to 1923]. İstanbul: T&K Press; Mayıs 2015.
14. A.{D.VN.MHM.d 19. BOA (Presidency of the Republic of Türkiye Directorate of State Archives)
15. A.{D.VN.MHM.d 3. BOA (Presidency of the Republic of Türkiye Directorate of State Archives)
16. A.{D.VN.MHM.d 22. BOA (Presidency of the Republic of Türkiye Directorate of State Archives)
17. Üçel-Aybet G. Avrupalı Seyyahların Gözünden Osmanlı Dünyası ve İnsanları (1530-1699) [The Ottoman World and People in the Eyes of European Travelers (1530-1699)]. İstanbul: 2003.
18. Görmez M, Özafşar ME, Ünal İH, Yavuz Ünal, Erul B, editors. Hadislerle İslam [Islam with Hadith]. Vol. 4. Ankara: Diyanet İşleri Başkanlığı Press; 2014.
19. Boyar E, Fleet K. Osmanlı İstanbul'unun Toplumsal Tarihi [Social History of Ottoman Istanbul]. Second Edition. İstanbul: Türkiye İş Bankası Kültür Yayınları Press; 2017.
20. Yıldırım N. İstanbul'un Kolera İle Tanışması: 1831 Salgını [Istanbul's Meeting with Cholera: The 1831 Epidemic]. Toplumsal Tarih. 2020 Nisan;316:62-66.
21. Panzac D. Osmanlı İmparatorluğu'nda Veba (1700-1850) [Plague in the Ottoman Empire (1700-1850)]. İstanbul: Tarih Vakfı Yurt Press; 1997.
22. Çelebi E. Evliyâ Çelebi Seyahatnâmesi Topkapı Sarayı Kütüphanesi Bağdat 308 Numaralı Yazmanın Transkripsiyonu-Dizini [Evliyâ Çelebi's Travel Book, Topkapı Palace Library, Transcription-Index of Manuscript No. 308 in Baghdad]. Kahraman SA, Dağlı Y, Dankoff R, editors. 8. Kitap, İstanbul: YKY Press; 2003.
23. Freely J. Evliya Çelebi'nin İstanbul'u [Evliya Çelebi's Istanbul]. Translated: Müfit Günay, Second Edition. İstanbul: YKY Press; Mart 2003.
24. A.{D.VN.MHM.d 5. BOA (Presidency of the Republic of Türkiye Directorate of State Archives)
25. Yılmazçelik İ. XIX. Yüzyılın İlk Yarısında Diyarbakır (1790-1840) [Diyarbakır in the First Half of the 19th Century (1790-1840)]. Ankara: TTK Press; 1995.
26. Dereci Ş. Mekânsal Sabitleme'ye Bir Örnek: Mecburi İstasyon Olarak Beyrut Karantinahanesi [An Example of Spatial Fixation: Beirut Quarantine as a Mandatory Station]. History Studies. 2021 Nisan;13/2.
27. Sarıyıldız G. Karantina [Quarantine], *DİA*, Vol. 24, İstanbul: Türkiye Diyanet Vakfı Press; 2001. pp. 463-465.

28. Conner CD. Halkın Bilim Tarihi Madenciler, Ebeler ve “Basit Tamirciler” [People’s History of Science Miners, Midwives, and “Simple Fixers”]. Third Edition. Ankara: TÜBİTAK Popüler Bilim Kitapları 444; June 2013.
29. Seetzen, UJ. İstanbul Günlükleri ve Anadolu’da Yolculuk 12 Aralık 1802-22 Haziran 1803 [Istanbul Diaries and Journey in Anatolia 12 December 1802-22 June 1803]. Vol. 2. First Edition. İstanbul 2017.
30. Şahin Ö. Muğla Karabaşının (Lavandula Stoechas L.) Yiyecek ve İçecek Olarak Değerlendirilmesine Yönelik Bir Öneri [A Suggestion for the Evaluation of Muğla Karabaşı (Lavandula Stoechas L.) as Food and Beverage]. Journal of Tourism and Gastronomy Studies. 2017; 5(2):37-49.
31. Kaplan EN, Çakı, MN, Paşa S. Lavandula Stoechas (Karabaş Otu) Bitki Özütünden Kozmetik Ürün Eldesi [Preparation of Cosmetic Product from Lavandula Stoechas (Black Head) Plant Extract]. UMÜFED Uluslararası Batı Karadeniz Mühendislik ve Fen Bilimleri Dergisi. 2019;1(1):24-37.
32. Köse F. Osmanlılarda Nevruzîyye Geleneklerine Tarihsel Açından Bakış [A Historical Perspective on Nevruzîyya Traditions in the Ottomans]. Ekev Akademi Dergisi. 2012 Bahar;16(51):93-102.
33. Çelebi E. Evliyâ Çelebi Seyahatnâmesi [Travel Book of Evliya Celebi]. Kahraman SA, Dağlı Y, editors. 6. Kitap. İstanbul: YKY Press; Haziran 2002.
34. Çelebi E. Evliyâ Çelebi Seyahatnâmesi-Topkapı Sarayı Kütüphanesi Bağdat 306, Süleymaniye Kütüphanesi Pertev Paşa 462, Süleymaniye Kütüphanesi Hacı Beşir Ağa 452 Numaralı Yazmaların Mukayeseli Transkripsiyonu-Dizini [Evliyâ Çelebi Seyahatname-Comparative Transcription-Index of Manuscripts Numbered Topkapı Palace Library Baghdad 306, Süleymaniye Library Pertev Paşa 462, Süleymaniye Library Hacı Beşir Ağa 452]. Dağlı Y, Kahraman SA, Dankoff R, editors. 9. Kitap. İstanbul: YKY Press; Mart 2005.
35. Naîmâ M. Târih-i Naîmâ [Naima’s History]. İpşirli M, editor. Vol. 4. Ankara: TTK Press; 2007.
36. Aşık M. Menâzirü’l-Avâlim [Perspectives of the worlds]. Ak M, editor. Vol. 3. Ankara: TTK Press; 2007.
37. Çelebi K. Cihânnümâ [View of the World]. Öztürk S, editor. İstanbul: İstanbul Büyükşehir Belediyesi Kültür A.Ş. Press; Mayıs 2010.
38. Serrano, M, Sanz Y. Türkiye’nin Dört Yılı 1552-1556 [Four Years of Turkey 1552-1556]. İstanbul: Kervan Kitapçılık Press; 1979.
39. Wratislaw W. Baron W. Wratislaw’ın Anıları “16. Yüzyıl Osmanlı İmparatorluğundan Çizgiler” [Memoirs of Baron W. Wratislaw “Notes from the 16th Century Ottoman Empire”]. Second Edition, İstanbul: AD Press; September 1996.
40. Slavicek LC. The Black Death. New York: Chelsea House Publishers; 2008.
41. Çelebi E. Evliyâ Çelebi Seyahatnâmesi [Travel Book of Evliya Celebi]. Kahraman SA, Dağlı Y, editors. 3. Kitap. İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Press; 1999.
42. Çelebi E. Evliyâ Çelebi Seyahatnâmesi [Travel Book of Evliya Celebi]. Dağlı Y, Kahraman SA, editors. 4. Kitap, İstanbul: Yapı Press, Mart 2001.
43. Çelebi E. Evliyâ Çelebi Seyahatnâmesi [Travel Book of Evliya Celebi]. Kurşun Z, Kahraman SA, Dağlı Y, editors. 2. Kitap, İstanbul: YKY Press; 2006.

44. Çelebi E. Evliyâ Çelebi Seyahatnâmesi [Travel Book of Evliya Celebi]. Kahraman SA, Dağlı Y, Dankoff R, editors. 10. Kitap, İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Press; Ekim 2007.
45. Şahin K. Ladik-Hamamayağı Kaplıcaları [Ladik-Hamamayagi Hot Springs]. Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi. 1997 Samsun;10(1):181-194.
46. Moltke HV. Moltke'nin Türkiye Mektupları [Moltke's Letters from Turkey]. İstanbul: Remzi Kitabevi Press; 1969.
47. Şimşek, K. Tarih-i Cevdet'e Göre Napolyon ve Mısır Meselesi [Napoleon and Egyptian Question in Tarih-I Cevdet] [dissertation]. Denizli: Pamukkale Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Tarih Anabilim Dalı; 2012.
48. Barkey K. Eşkîyalar ve Devlet Osmanlı Tarzı Devlet Merkezileşmesi [Bandits and the State. Ottoman Style State Centralization]. Second Edition. İstanbul: Tarih Vakfı Yurt Yayınları Press; Kasım 2011.

Submitted: 07/10/2021

Reviewed: 19/10/2021

Accepted: 26/10/2021